

										Final Considerations		Q = QUESTION	
										Q28	Extra	P = PARTICIPANT	
										P1		contato@retrum.com.nr	
										P2			
										P3			
										P4		contato@niobiumstudios.com	
										P5			
										P6		leonardo.g_m@hotmail.com	
										P7	Unless you think you're going to work for a game company with over 500 people, which doesn't exist in Brazil, forget about being a UX Designer as a solo career. UX is an important part of the knowledge required to develop games, and should be inherent to any Game Designer or UI Designer. If the goal is to work in fintech, then UX as a solo career will be in demand in the market.		
										P8		luiza@plotkids.com	
										P9			
										P10		daniocesareu@gmail.com	
										P11	I believe UX is an area that, in the gaming industry, should have synergy with game design and UI art.	Sim	
										P12	I don't know much about UX.	kellenkyo@hotmail.com	
										P13	Comprehensive research, which may be further detailed at a later time.	contato@mimagames.com.br	
										P14			
										P15	In general, UX will depend on the game style, since the game mechanics don't always aim to make the user's life easier. For example, tutorials or progressive difficulty may not be well-suited to a specific game style. Can you see these nuances of UX across different types of games?	ricwag.si@gmail.com	
										P16			
										P17		rouem.dev@gmail.com	
										P18			
										P19			
										P20		alexandre2o@gmail.com	
										P21	As a professional in the field and a gamer, I realize that UX is what makes the difference in having a complete experience. Forgetting this point means the game can be very well programmed, artistically beautiful, but very boring.	patricia@painfulsmile.com.br	
										P22	I believe the term "UX" has been used as a buzzword in academic circles. UX is not a technique; it's something that always exists in any piece of design, and any design process is always concerned with meeting the affordances of its users. I believe the way "UX" has been handled in non-designer circles seems more like a fad than a real understanding of how intrinsic UX is to any development.		
										P23		rennan.gpenha@dumativa.com	
										P24			
										P25		contact@moonmind.studio	
										P26			
										P27	I've noticed there are few qualified professionals to address UX in the field of electronic games.	sydenstricker.sony@gmail.com	
										P28			
										P29		rvertulo@gmail.com	
										P30		contato@hs.dev.br	
										P31			
										P32		radacia@gmail.com	
										P33	Being a sole proprietorship and consequently needing to pay attention to all areas of development and business activities, it becomes a great challenge to find time to study UX further and effectively implement more formal processes, especially when the game being developed is in a constant state of evolution, but it is recognized that this is not the ideal scenario.	contato@sendoestudio.com.br	

